

The insights of an 'African Astronomy,' and an 'African Nuclear Physics' reveal the energetic symmetry of our Universe. This flags up the potential we humans have, to create an healing process for the phenomena of nuclear radiation.

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Abstract.

1. Modern Astronomy sees our planetary system from the outside, whereas an experiential 'African Astronomy' looks from the inside and sees how the light from the Moon and the light from the Sun combine in the course of a year to create a 'photon' that lights the Earth and everything living on this planet.

This insight helps us see how the same heavenly blend of feminine and masculine forces work together in our family systems to light our children.

This parallel energetic pattern indicates that our Universe is a system of family systems, one within the other.

2. Nuclear physics has determined that there are 'four-interactive-forces' in each and every atom. An 'African nuclear physics' recognises how these four energetic qualities are equally here at work within and between us humans. They are especially evident in family life.

The same energy is us as is in the atoms implies that atoms are the family systems of the particle population, and that the atomic particles are social and sentient, the same as ourselves. In this mood, look again at the Mushroom Cloud and see how it portrays the union of the feminine and masculine 'entities' which form themselves from the copious quantities of energy released out of matter by the fission process.

3. The history of the discovery and exploration and exploitation of Africa, and subsequently of the Atomic World, by the same set of European nations, reveals the colonial nature of these the two parallel processes. History is repeating itself. What goes on inside our nuclear reactors is the modern equivalent of the African Slave Trade.

4. In a quest to portray the physics and the metaphysics of the 94 elements of matter, this chapter outlines how a tabular and a spiral form of The Periodic Table of the Elements provides a clear picture of the physical and chemical nature of the elements on the one hand, and on the other, shows how the elements are like way-stations on the one path that brings the particles like pilgrims from the fringe settlement of Uranium to the central stable elementary state we know as Hydrogen.

The same dualistic kind of inquiry helps us see how the fissile isotope U-235 is being sheltered and mentored by the bulk of the passive U-238 isotope. The enrichment of Uranium is a totally un-natural process. The equivalent at best to ethnic cleansing.

5. The energetic symmetry that infuses our Universe indicates the potential we humans have to create a remedial process whereby we might land photons of our Love and Light amongst the fissioned particles, to determine if this is beneficial for them. As it surely will be for us.

In contrast to our White-man's technology, which works to 'split the atom', African society looks capable of developing a collective spiritual process able to 'heal the atom'.

Introduction. I was privileged to be born in Kenya, in 1943. Along with a brother and sister, we lived in a fairly remote and sparsely-populated district where our English father was an official with the British Colonial Administration. Our Scottish mother typed his reports, made our clothes, supervised the household and sent us outside to play during the day, and then sleep under mosquito nets, in the starry nights that pulsed with the mating call of cicadas.

Gratitude then for a simple and safe childhood amongst earthy friendly African people. We kids were in large part cared for by Maria, a Nandi woman from Western Kenya, engaged by our mother. I think of Maria as one source of a profound sympathy for Africa which made a home in me, alongside of the Britishness of my upbringing.

The district where we lived was without electricity, so our home was softly-lit by oil lamps in the evening, while outside, the semi-desert landscape was soft-lit by the changing light of the Moon at night, and by the Sun's hot bright light during the day.

I saw on many occasions how these two heavenly bodies were the same size.

I observed an eclipse of the Sun by the Moon through a piece of smoked glass, and saw how these two bodies are visually the exact same size. And no one thought to tell me otherwise.

Then, at around the age of ten, we kids were sent to be schooled in Scotland. Here I learnt about the Sun-centred nature of our planetary system and how the Moon is but a minor satellite locked in orbit around the Earth.

I will fast-forward this account to the time when I was an adult, now working in Canada as a geologist, now married to an Irish woman, and with three young children. I recollect the evening when we were out walking with the children and marvelling at the night sky and I overheard the kids comment on the identical size of the Moon, which was rising in the East, with the Sun, that was setting on the western horizon. Then I remembered my own childhood experiences of their parity and the Garden of Eden feeling of being safe in a world watched over by these two reliable heavenly figures who were the exact same size.

By this time, I had learnt that the Moon and the Sun share the same period of rotation. This simple piece of information had a big effect on me. I had reconciled myself to accept that their apparent identical size was pure coincidence. To then discover there is another profound synchronicity within this same heavenly partnership, and learn that this too is regarded as mere coincidence ... was simply too much for me to accept. I remember my bewilderment and disbelief on hearing this information and my determination to look again at and into this heavenly conundrum.

Mapping our experience of the Light that lights the Earth.

I feel it necessary to comment on how world society has changed in my lifetime. In large measure by the rising tide of power and rank of women in society, and for feminine values everywhere. In hindsight I would say that I found this process supportive of my general interest in the subjective nature of universal phenomena. For example, it gave me leeway to contemplate and develop a metaphysical view of our planetary system.

While I had assimilated and liked the Solar System concept, I also registered how Copernicus and now Modern Astronomy take for granted the ever-changing qualities of the Light that lights this planet.

Our masculine mind, which I identify as our 'left-brain', excels with its ability to study and analyse and describe the objective nature of phenomena. Without leaving our planet, we have determined the diameter of the Sun as 1.39 million km., while that of the Moon is 3475 km. This information satisfies and hugely influences our rational mind, gives it an authority and outlook that then overwhelms the observations of our 'right-brain', the home in my understanding for the pre-conceptual views of children, or aboriginal people, and home too for the 'feminine gaze'.

These were the elements of the intellectual conundrum I was trying to work out for myself. In the process, I felt it useful to map my experience of the different kinds of light coming from the Moon and from the Sun in the course of a year. It has to be for a whole year, since this is a unit of time for this particular lighting effect. I explained the exercise to the children and heard their misgivings at the thought of sitting outside for a year with pencil and paper while trying to follow my plan.

Their response helped me realise that we only need to track the light coming from this heavenly pair for a month, for a single lunar cycle, and then we can multiply its experiential shape twelve times or thereabouts, to create an idea of the whole shape of the year-long lighting effect we feel we are within.

In fact, by recording the position of the Moon and the Sun at the same time each day, we largely eliminate the effect of the Earth's daily rotation, which otherwise keeps turning us away from observing and charting the different qualities of the light coming from these two heavenly bodies.

An experiential astronomy seeks to record our experiences of the light coming from each of these heavenly bodies. It is the quality of the two different streams of light that we are seeking to record and value. We are not concerned in this study with the size or appearance or material construction of the light bulbs. We are not particularly interested in how far away (or close) they might be. It is our experience of the quality and quantity of the light coming from them that is important.

We see the Sun's light as pretty constant. It changes of course with the seasons, loses some of its warmth and brightness in the winter, becomes more intense in the summer. This is a consequence of the tilt of the Earth, and of the changing 'thickness' of the Earth's atmosphere. Effects that I have sought to filter out. Sunlight generally has a constant quality, being as a steady stream of bright energy that illuminates the Earth each and every day. In the course of a month, we observe how the source of this stream of particle energy moves 30 degrees right to left in front of the fixed curtain of stars that are in effect stationary in the background. The year-long apparent movement through 360 degrees marks the size and duration of one complete lighting cycle.

Meanwhile, the light we experience coming from the Moon is far more changeable during this same period. We register how moonlight first appears as a distant thin crescent which then, day after day, night after night, grows larger and seemingly comes closer, until the time of the Full Moon, which is the half way point of the lunar cycle with its wave form effect. Now the moonlight conveys a range of motherly qualities, being comforting and watchful and approving.

After this, the moonlight began to thin in quantity and quality, or so it feels. The tranquil nature of moonlight diminishes in the waning period, as the light fades and recedes into the distance. Finally, this quite neutral and washed-out form of light disappears into the Sun, or so it seems to us.

This composite image represents our overall experience of the whole field of Light which forms around the Earth in a year, which is a quantum unit of time for this whole lighting system. The Moon in fact completes between twelve and thirteen of her wave-like cycles during the course of a year.

My drawing simplifies her activity to twelve complete cycles. So it is an approximation of our annual heavenly experience. The latitude of the observer is bound to influence the overall shape of this annual experiential effect.

Now look with scientific acumen at this annual effect, and see in our mind's eye how the Earth is within a pulsating field of particle and waveform energy. A field that has all the attributes of what our work in the Atomic realm has identified and knows as a 'photon'.

Thoughts for the physics and metaphysics of astronomy.

We have come to think of photons as 'units of whole Light', that exist primarily at the atomic level. The ancient understanding of 'Light' being as a Constant within the Universe, makes it sensible for us 'observers of the Universe', to expect to find the same light-giving, light-forming phenomena of a photon to be present and at work in each and every dimension of this remarkably symmetrical universal system we are within.

The photon effect that lights the Earth, along with the Solar System concept, form themselves as holograms in our mind's eye. We humans, we Humanity, are the species with the discipline and intellectual acumen able to observe and document two different ways of viewing the very same energetic system.

The outside view of our planetary system, cultivated by Modern Astronomy, has created a map which shows where the Sun and the planets are in relationship to each other. With this knowledge we can navigate spacecraft to rendezvous with the other planets. Amongst other things, the map portrays the extended blended family nature of our planetary system. Something untoward seems to have happened a long time ago which required Father Sun to take in, or take on, the 'outer planets', who are clearly offspring from another planetary system. Well done Father Sun. Your energy and generosity are obviously sufficient for this duty. Here is an historical event that deserves further investigation.

Meanwhile, the inside view charts our experience of the wholesome effect created by the heavenly partnership of the Moon and the Sun working together to love and light the homely planet Earth. Whereas the outside view values the physical, the inside view registers the metaphysical. I am not entirely secure with this thought, but I am inclined to think that the physical is hugely influenced by the metaphysical.

The 'heavenly photon' that lights the Earth is of an apparent magnitude that matches the scale of the Solar System. The form of this whole visceral wheeling effect can not be seen from the outside. It is strictly an experiential reckoning. The concept and experience of the photon effect that lights the Earth provides a fairly simple and immediate explanation for the unparalleled healthiness and fecundity of this planet. The unified yet singular effect of an integrated field of the Moon's feminine power and the Sun's masculine strength pulsating routinely (say twelve rhythmic pulses per annum) around this planet (for say two or three billion years), feels cause enough to explain the abundance of life forms that have developed and evolved within this empowering field of whole Light.

Here is a working system that I think deserves to be seen as a universal process. My thesis, by which I mean my personal experience, is that when we combine perceptions of the physics and the metaphysics of phenomena, then we engage the two kinds of knowledge that together allow us to see the universal nature of our Universe. Our dual-processor brain is designed for this kind of dualistic analysis. Then it can generate holograms that combine the different qualities of information that our left and right-side brains are able to distinguish and store. In this context, I would say that the enduring energetic family-like system of the Sun, Moon and Earth looks to be as a template for identifying or modelling the purposeful union of masculine and feminine forces in many other settings.

Here in our familiar homely Earthly setting, I would indicate how our very own personal family systems, that we have grown up within, or create with a partner, provides a multitude of examples whereby we can observe how the 'photon dynamic' is hugely formative within us humans. It codes fundamental aspects of our family lives, and formulates this same behaviour within many other species who populate this planet.

This train of thought leads me to think that the concept of a 'planetary photon' might well serve the inquiry going on these days and years, to identify exoplanets which might be conducive for life to develop. What is good for us, for this planet, already serves as a benchmark for investigations that seek to identify planetary bodies that exist in the same setting. While a 'photon of whole Light' is an experiential effect, and not normally discernible from the outside, yet I imagine there are ways of observing and measuring planetary or star systems for data that matches the Sun/Moon configuration that benefits this planet.

The 'heavenly photon effect', which I allude to in this paper as an "African Astronomy", is the antithesis of the intellectual process that studies the heavens and created the body of knowledge we know as Modern Astronomy.

The African view attends to the nature of the whole experience of being within the heavenly system we are within. It is more catholic than protestant. Makes more use of the intellectual acumen of our 'right brain', in contrast to Modern Astronomy which gives unprecedented authority to the intellectual processes of our 'left brain'.

An African Astronomy feels for what it sees, whereas Modern Astronomy sees what it already thinks. Experience on the one hand, concept on the other. I would add to this a personal observation, that we are formed by experience more than we are by concept.

An African Astronomy observes the subjective nature of the whole heavenly effect that we observers are within. This recognises the matriarchal behaviour of the Moon and the chieftain-like qualities and duties of the Sun. This, to my mind, is a universal process and effect, and not in any way accidental or co-incidental.

I would further qualify this dualistic account by saying that Modern Astronomy is a 'White-Man's Astronomy', and what I refer to as an African Astronomy is symbolically a 'Black Woman's Astronomy'.

I have good memories of the Nandi woman, Maria from Western Kenya, whom our mother engaged for several years to care for us white children. She did indeed care for us. She was indeed like the Moon: observant, tranquil, quietly and constantly present and patient with us. She influenced our whole household with her even temperament and respect for the many forms of life that moved through our house. Lizards on the ceiling, columns of ants making their way across the concrete floor, snakes skulking about in the shamba. I don't recall talking with her about the Moon and the Sun being the same size, but why would I, since it was so obvious.

Thank you. I am glad to write about astronomical observations that are clearly and deeply informative about the remarkable symmetry and wholeness and universality of the lighting effect that the Earth and us earthlings are within. It is the union of our Western mind's patriarchal outside view of our planetary system, with an experiential matriarchal African view from the inside, that I find allows us to realise the universal nature of the Light that lights our world.

This fairly personal insight gains authority and credence when paired with the knowledge determined by physicists that photons are 'frequent flyers' at the atomic level of this universal system that we are all within. The image posted here seeks to illustrate the existence of photons within the different dimensions that together create our experience of a Universe.

The photons that we humans form are the most difficult to see, because we are within them, and their form is fairly flexible, and never as specific and reliable as the heavenly one that lights the Earth.

Nonetheless, the metaphysical perception of the existence of 'photons' helps affirm the concept of an "energetic symmetry" that infuses or pervades the several or many dimension that together form our experience of being within a Uni-verse.

The scientific method, which virtually "rules the roost" these days and years, thinks it clever to ignore metaphysical information and subjective effects. Yet it is 'subjective effects' that allows us to recognise the 'energetic symmetry' that forms and informs every level of this universal system that we are within. An energetic symmetry that is even here within us humans.

I know I keep repeating myself but it was this realisation of the dualistic intellect that is our birthright, that I pressed into service to help me approach and see the beautifully-balanced symbiotic lighting system that we are within.

My respect for our dualistic intellect was and continues to be affirmed simply by stepping outside and both seeing and feeling that I am inside a cocoon of whole Light. Meanwhile, even as I sorted out for myself the experiential form of the photon effect, my concern and curiosity about the Atomic World and the nuclear subject was also asking for my attention. By now I felt more informed about my own process of inquiry. I saw how nuclear physicists had adopted the scientific outlook and methodology that informed the generation of astronomers, typically Copernicus and Galileo and Isaac Newton, and applied it to their investigation of the atom and the Atomic realm. I could feel it wasn't enough to focus exclusively on the physics. We need a working sense of the metaphysics, which then we gives us a sense of the wholeness, and equally the holiness, of this new world that we have found our way into.

All of this, I want to say, is or was a consequence of the measure of an 'African consciousness' that I acquired from Maria, from my childhood in Kenya.

I was by this time working as a geologist in Canada when I became involved in a search for uranium. That work made me curious about the nature of the energy in the atom, about the 'four-interactive-forces' that nuclear physics has identified in each and every atom. Here was information that I began to turn over in my mind. It so happened that my wife and I were hugely busy at that time with raising our three children. This helped more than anything to immerse me in the dynamics of family life. I found myself in a delightfully crazy space where I was trying to acclimatise myself to the different processes and experiences that formed the bulk of each day and my duties as a new father.

Slowly slowly it dawned on me how the four-interactive-forces that physics has identified in each and every atom, that these same four kinds of energy were (and are) equally here at work within and between us humans. They are especially evident in family life, in family systems, little or large.

The same energy in the atoms as is here within and between us humans. From this I am inclined to see that atoms are the family systems of the particle population. And that the particle population are the indigenous native inhabitants of the Atomic World.

In the next section of this 'paper', I will describe the 'four forces' in more detail, that others can share the insights about this suite of four energetic qualities being here amongst us humans, the same as they are amongst and between the atomic particles. You will find no doubt that I keep repeating myself. The energetic similarity of atoms and human families, the same as with the photon dynamic that lights this planet, that works in our family lives, all of this goes to affirm the energetic symmetry of our Universe. And this, in the end and the beginning, suggest how we Humanity might develop remedial procedures that can address the nuclear issues that trouble our times.

galactic magnitude

sun, moon, earth system

human family

particle families

2. Whereas nuclear physics has determined that there are 'four-interactive-forces' in each and every atom, an 'African nuclear physics' recognises how these four energetic qualities are equally present and at work here in our family lives.

In this mood, look again at the Mushroom Cloud and see how it portrays the marriage of the feminine and masculine 'entities' who form themselves from the copious quantities of energy released out of matter by the fission process.

Introduction. I came to the nuclear subject as a consequence of working as a geologist in Canada, where I was involved in a search for uranium. That work made me curious about the nature of the energy in the atoms. I firstly learnt about the 'four-interactive-forces', which nuclear physics has determined are in each and every atom. These four forces are known everywhere as:

Gravity and **Electromagnetism** (which are long range forces), and **The Strong** and **the Weak** Nuclear Forces (which are short range forces (in other words, they only function within the boundary of each atom)). Together they form what we know casually as 'nuclear energy'.

I recognised early on how physics identifies these forces on the basis of their objective properties. Being as I am an introspective person, this caused me to wonder about their subjective qualities. What, for instance, might they feel like.

During this time, when I was wondering about the subjective qualities of the 'four forces', my wife and I were busy as anything with raising our three young children. Our home was brimful with the children's activities and demands and needs. In the hurly burly of it all, I slowly came to see how the four energetic qualities that physics has identified in the atoms, these same energetic qualities were equally here at work and play in the daily dynamic of family life. I now see how they are in every family system, little or large. And not just in us humans. The 'four forces' look to be at work in every species, and present at every level of this multi-tiered universal system that we are within. Here is how I have come to see the subjective qualities of the 'four forces'.

Gravity, often categorised as the first of the four forces, is a quality I easily recognise in myself. I am a serious character, full of gravity, 'heavy' about everyday subjects. Gravititas dominates my demeanour. Gravity is clearly a masculinity quality. It finds expression in me as a fairly authoritarian father. The same quality that was in my father, and his. Nothing especially new then in my archetypal make up.

I dwell on the analogy of **Gravity** being synonymous with **Masculinity** because it exemplifies the dualistic process whereby we can take an objective description of physical phenomena (such as this energetic force), and by dwelling on our experience of how this force feels and functions, we can identify the metaphysical and subjective nature of this universal effect.

Whereas **Gravity** is an ambitious and commanding vertical force ... **Electromagnetism**, on the other hand, is an entirely feminine power.

Electromagnetism, physically and psychically, is a friendly family-centred motherly power that emanates and spreads horizontally from her centre. The magnetic power of this forces reaches out to permeate the surrounding area and hears and feels the emotional state of everything in this territory. At home in a family setting, this is the inquisitive mothering consciousness that likes to know how everyone in the house is doing, how they are feeling, and what their needs are.

The short-range forces:

Physics knows the **Strong Nuclear Force** as the 'binding energy' that holds each atom together. It is a collective elastic-like power that works to stabilise every atom and every family system. It is an essential quality because competing forces continually arise within every atom or family unit: forces which threaten to split the unit apart. I sense that the **Strong Force** is equivalent to the "family spirit", to the collective energy, the love and loyalty, little or large that each member/particle of the family/atom contributes to the whole system.

In contrast, the **Weak Nuclear Force** is a miniscule quantity of energy that was discounted as experimental error in the early days of particle physics. Further investigation then determined that this is indeed an individual force, and its identifying characteristics are that it only functions across a very short distance, and only exists for a brief moment of time. But in that moment, it is more powerful than all the other forces. Now, doesn't this sound and feel like sexual energy. The **Weak Force** works as a catalyst, and combines with **Electromagnetism** and **Gravity** to make them interact and be fruitful and productive.

I would mention here that astrophysicists calculated in the 1930's how the 'four forces' were seeded into our universal system in the beginning moments of the Big Bang. Around this same time, nuclear physicists determined how these four forces are in each and every atom. Thus we know full well they are in the macrocosm and the microcosm. Now we dearly needs to realise how the 'four forces' are equally here at work in us humans. We can not recognise this if we close the door on subjective data and effect. Once we realise the social and spiritual nature of these forces, how they work together to create and maintain family systems, then our Universe becomes yet more sensible and uniform in its processes and behaviour.

The band-width of the information about the 'four forces' indicates they are universal forces. To my mind, this means that however we might seek to identify them, we will in the end only recognise the qualities that match our particular interest. Physics knows them for their physical properties. The religious for their spiritual qualities. In the home, we know the 'four forces' for their homely and domestic and social nature.

"The Four-interactive-Forces" and the different nomenclature we give to them, according to the purpose of our inquiry.		
The terminology of Nuclear Physics, as it identifies the objective properties in each atom.	Domestic household language as we recognise the subjective nature of each force in the family.	Christian synonyms that seek to name the spiritual quality of each force.
Gravity	Masculine Strength	Light of God
Electromagnetism	Feminine Power	Amos
The Strong Nuclear Force	Family Group Energy	Agape
The Weak Nuclear Force	Sexual Energy	Eros

This table conveys the family-centred nature of this multi-tiered universal system we are all within. Here is a good place to re-iterate how my experience of these four forces indicates that three of them are forms of Love, while the fourth is a form of Light.

Meanwhile, observe how, in our modern era, nuclear physics has grabbed the talking stick and thinks these 'four forces' are theirs alone. This is not so. They live in all of us, and all of the time. Our civil nature needs to equally claim ownership and responsibility for their sensible use.

The metaphysics of the Mushroom Cloud.

The same energy in the atoms as in us humans suggests we must expect to find the same energetic processes going on in the particle world as engage us humans in our world. In this context, look again at the Mushroom Cloud that forms itself in the aftermath of every nuclear detonation.

This series of photographs come from a nuclear weapon test carried out by the French military in the South Pacific, circa 1970. I have however borrowed the first image from an American test, because it very clearly shows the formative beginning moment of this almighty process. The photographs allow us to see how the copious quantities of masculine (Gravity) and feminine (Electromagnetism) energy released out of the atoms by the fission process, then form (at the speed of Light) the two pantomime-like "energetic entities" that together initiate and create the whole Mushroom Cloud drama.

The Mushroom Cloud portrays the meeting and marriage of the feminine and masculine "energetic entities" who form themselves (at the speed of Light) from the energy released out of the atoms by the fission process.

Young lovers

The married couple. Her power the equal of his strength.

Each partner busy developing their own talents. His ambition is

to reach his full potential. While she cloaks herself with emotional powers.

Her destiny is to be the motherly queen, supported by his princely gravity.

Observe in the first image, how the muscular masculine 'entity' rises with love and longing to meet the soft rounded honeybun-figure of the feminine 'entity', waiting above where he is. We can see already the relationship forming between them. The Mushroom Cloud is basically a visual record of their union and indeed, their marriage to each other.

We can recognise and follow their process because it is entirely similar to our human experience of the marriage cycle. The atomic version completes itself in about fifty seconds of our time, whereas we humans can take fifty years to fulfil the same phases that they work through, in their Atomic World existence.

Nuclear fission works for us, in our reactors, by breaking up the atoms of uranium. By this means we gain access to the heat of the Light quotient that is in each and every atom. Light (amalgamated with Gravity) is one of the four forces. The three other forces (which are forms of Love) are discarded because they have no calorific value, and are useless for boiling water, which is the primary purpose of a nuclear reactor.

In the vein of inquiry that values subjective data, our nuclear work allows us to see how the atomic particles are social and sentient, the same as we are. They are in turn as small to us as we are small to the Sun. This kind of understanding helps us see them as the children of this universal system that we are all within. Gulliver would have recognised all of this if he was traveling today. The same energy, the same energetic processes amongst the particles as is here in us humans allows us to recognise how 'radioactivity' is a measure of the emotional distress of the fissioned particles. Fission works for us by annihilating the family systems that together create the particle nation of Uranium. This is the reality we dearly need to see and own.

The last clear image we have of the whole fission process shows how the "feminine archetype" has transformed herself into a regal and matriarchal entity. She has the demeanour and deportment of a Queen. She is commanding and matronly. This surely indicates the quality of the consciousness that has developed within her, during this whole marriage cycle. See, by the way, also how the fabric of the Queen's electromagnetic dress is torn. We can see swirls of Mr Gravity's golden energy, the metaphysical stuff that forms his upright frame, is now leaking out of the enclosing gown, yet continues to migrate upwards.

Upwards is indeed the main direction of the Atomic man's enthusiasm and drive to get as high as he can with his life energy.

Everyone has countless reasons for believing in the separate self. For staying away from evidence of our universal nature. Observe the fission process from this part of ourselves and see how we are watching a marriage ceremony at the beginning, and then how this 'energetic universal couple', created from the energy that was in the atoms, then live collaboratively together while developing their particular talents.

This is an entirely sensible and symmetrical Universe. The same universal forces are at work and play between us humans, as are between and amongst the atomic particles, as are upstairs between the Sun and the Moon.

The nuclear weapon tests reveal as never before the longing for the creative co-operative union that is between feminine and masculine forms of energy. The very forces that our nuclear technology casually releases out of their shared bed in matter.

Do the military or the nuclear institutions know this? Not yet. They have been schooled and school themselves to look away. This is primarily a civilian observation. In which case, we civilians must develop civil ways to engage with this deeper knowledge.

3. The story of the discovery and exploration and exploitation of Africa by the "white-man", is identical to the discovery and exploration and exploitation of the Atomic World some two hundred years later, by the same European nations (with the British again as front-runner), but now joined by the Americans.

In other words, nuclear reactors are the modern equivalent of the African Slave Trade. History is repeating itself.

The history of Europe's involvement with Africa began with Portuguese sailors venturing south from their home ports, and mapping the coastline of the African continent. Then the other sea-faring nations of Europe, the British and the Dutch, followed suit and in due course established settlements in South Africa and trading posts (with a fort or two) where the continental rivers discharged into the sea.

Even before the Europeans arrived in Africa, a slave trade was operating at a local level. But now, with the British jumbo boats capable of transporting several hundred men and women in one vessel, there was the capacity to ship ten million or more African people across the Atlantic Ocean to work as slaves in the sugar cane plantations and cotton fields and mills being developed in the Americas and the Caribbean.

An inquiry by British physicists into the nature of the atom could not help but use the same resources and mindset that had successfully mapped and then colonised much of Africa. My reading of the situation is that because the focus of the physicists was on determining the physical properties of the particles in the atom, then no one saw or thought of the atomic particles as an whole, as being the indigenous native population who occupy the sub-continent of "Atomica".

as an whole, as being the indigenous native population who occupy the sub-continent of "Atomica".

The realisation of the copious quantities of energy locked up in the atoms led to the development of the atomic bomb. Then nuclear reactors were designed and built to use the same fission process to control the extraction of heat from the atoms.

A comparison of the fission process going on in a nuclear reactor with the capture and transportation of African tribal people to a distant lands, where their physical energy is harnessed to power the new industries being developed in the Americas ... is a slow to realise but virtually identical story.

There is virtually no difference in universal terms between the African Slave Trade and what goes on inside each and every nuclear reactors, except here the devastation of the atoms, the family systems of the particle population, goes on out of sight, in an whole other dimension. The operators of the reactors, guided by government regulations, take elaborate precautions to insure that no one will hear or feel the distress and sadness of the fissioned particles, the effect we know as radiation. To my mind, the radiation of the fissioned particles is synonymous with 'the Blues' of the African people obliged to work as slaves burnt-out and likely to remain blue for the next twenty thousand years or so.

The colonisation of Africa has come to an end but now the very same parties are busy with the colonisation of 'Atomica', and sell their electricity to civil society as a technically innovative energy that is beneficial for the climate change issue which now looms over the future. No mention is made by the advocates of nuclear electricity of the scorching pain and searing sadness that lives on in the vast population of fissioned particles.

When my interest in a metaphysical understanding of the nuclear subject reached a certain level, I sought work at **Dounreay, the nuclear reactor here in northern Scotland.**

I obtained work as a geological technician on a drill rig which was employed in an investigation of the geology and hydrology of the rock strata in the vicinity of the nuclear reactors. The investigation was to determine if the site would be suitable for the development of a nuclear waste repository. In the end, the engineers determined that it was not. Nonetheless, I was on site for six months and during this time had several profound realisations that I will outline here:

As I have already indicated, I grew up in a British colonial household and was entirely familiar with the outlook and attitudes of the British Colonial Service, which in turn reflects the imperious nature of Britain as a whole. I don't mean to be too judgmental and disapproving, since these values also found a home in me, more than I care to say. But in this instance, my experience of the orderly, disciplined, remote and cold-hearted view and treatment of the particle population being fissioned in the reactor brought me to see how we British, and indeed all the nuclear nations, are now working in the Atomic World as colonists. History is repeating itself. We British in particular, with our disdain for displays of emotion, think it clever and entirely acceptable to discount and ignore the extraordinary distress and despair of the fissioned particles. Because they become radioactive, they are seen as unclean, as lepers, as somehow guilty, to be avoided and not really our responsibility.

The knowledge that informs these comments comes from my experiences of visiting the site laboratory which was located beneath the reactor hall itself. One of the duties of the laboratory was to routinely examine the fuel rods which hold the pellets of uranium fuel that are being fissioned. The rods are carefully designed with an open lattice-like structure that both contains the pellets and also allows the liquid sodium to circulate through the rods and burning pellets, in order to recover the heat generated by the fission process. When the uranium fuel was spent, the by-now highly radioactive fuel rods were withdrawn from the reactor and conveyed by remote handling through a tunnel to a sealed chamber alongside the main room of the laboratory. Here workmen used glove boxes to reach through the chamber wall and cut up the used fuel rods, readying them for inspection.

In spite of the precautionary design of this process, the laboratory room became saturated with the feelings of radiation that simply penetrated the walls or leaked in through the glove boxes.

I visited the laboratory in the first instance with a guided party of visitors. The tour was led by two Scottish women who were employed, along with others, to staff the Visitors Centre. Our two were friendly and likeable with their bright and chatty nature so I was taken aback with how this changed as we passed through an air-lock in order to enter the laboratory. The two women became very strict and anxious as we entered this long and seemingly dark room, with its many consoles of flickering red and green lights. It was unusually hot in there. The air was heavy. We were all wearing outdoor clothes. No great surprise then when one of our party fainted.

I knew we would have to wait while this person recovered, so I retreated to a corner of the long room and sat on a box listening to the extraordinary sadness I felt welling up in me. I couldn't shake it off or explain it because I had joined the tour in really good heart. Then, after a while, I realised this was not my sadness, this was not my despair. These feelings were already here in this long room, with the glove boxes built into one wall, with windows above them which looked into the parallel chamber where fuel rods, some of them cut into pieces, were laid out in racks.

The Reactor Hall, Dounreay.

The person who fainted was better. The guides rounded us up and took us away from this gloomy place. That was the end of the tour. We handed in our dosimeters and hard hats. Tea and biscuits were served in the Visitors Centre. I sought out one of the guides and told her about the dark sadness I had felt in the lab. She turned away, there were tears in her eyes. She shook her head and wouldn't engage with me.

"This is the place", I remember saying to myself. Like the story of Bluebeard, who lavished his wife with gifts but warned her never ever to visit the chamber beneath his castle, even though he gave her a key to the door. Here was the one place in the whole operating system where there was a taste of the emotional content of radiation. A glimpse of the sentient nature of the particle world. The intense distress and sadness of the fissioned particles could not be contained. The feelings leaked through the walls and glove boxes or their windows. No one stayed there for long. The workmen were stoic, worked quickly and left.

Inside view of the empty Fast Breeder Reactor at Dounreay

I am able to write about this because I became acquainted in the canteen with the young graduate who was in charge of the laboratory. He had addressed us when we first entered the place, explaining its purpose to the tour party. I told him I was curious about the metaphysics of nuclear energy and felt he already had a sense of what I was talking about. In fact, he was sympathetic. It's not really possible to work in that kind of an environment without our imagination thinking outside the box. So he was okay with me then returning on other occasions when again I just sat quietly and felt into the feelings within that hot closed space.

I'll summarise my experience like this: how the effect was like sitting at the edge of an ocean of sombre emotions. From the ocean, a steady series of slow moving waves, waves of an immense sadness, washed over and through me. Slow moving waves of a hot dark sadness coming steadily from that black ocean. I tried conversing with the women in the Visitors Centre on a couple of occasions about my visits. They were appalled that I chose to go back. The laboratory was shrouded with taboo thoughts and feelings. They were spooked that I even sought to talk about my experience of the place. I'm sure they talked about it amongst themselves. But maybe not. I know they feared being on duty and having to go there.

On the other hand, I was quite upbeat and pleased with myself. This was exactly what I had coming looking for, even while I didn't really know what I was looking for. I told the men who managed the reactor, whom I would meet in the canteen, of my experiences. This one man in particular listened to me and said I was wasting their time. They were so busy dealing with the physics of the reactor, he said, they did not have the time to concern themselves with the metaphysics. But I am moved to say that this same man then asked me if I would like to talk with the Chief Physicist about my experience. This surprised me, but I said yes, and he said he would try and arrange it.

So I went one evening in the company van and parked in the winter darkness outside his home on the outskirts of Thurso. I rang the doorbell and his wife let me into the house, showed me to a study. He was a short-statured man, but highly energetic in his demeanour and he was not shy about immediately expressing his anger that someone like me had found his way into his operation. "Who had given me permission to visit the laboratory", he demanded of me straight off.

I told him I had joined a tour which at that time included a visit to the site laboratory. He was fuming. "You anti-nuclear people get in the way of progress", he shouted at me. I, meanwhile, was being a cool cucumber and told him that I wasn't anti-nuclear. In fact (and I emphasized this) I said I might well be the most pro-nuclear person on the whole site.

Our minds barely met. He was bristling with antipathy towards me. I said something along the lines of how useful I thought it was to have some sense of the emotional content of radiation. He could not really register the things I said. "That's not scientific!" was his main response. He said that he would have me fired if I went near the laboratory again. Then his wife brought in a tray of tea things and he turned on her and shouted at her. It was an absurd situation. I excused myself quite politely and left. The wife let me out and apologised for him, the loyal woman.

I thought later how impossible it would be for the tour guides to contribute their experiential knowledge of radiation to this hierarchical system of single-minded masculine authority. Our knowledge of the particle world and its sentience and endless pain is made virtually inaccessible by the institutionalised patriarchy and misogyny that is in the driving seat of an inquiry that I feel was originally the quest of Humanity to know the universal nature of our Universe. To know if there is life elsewhere in our Universe. This physics-only approach can not do it.

4. In a quest to further portray the physics and the metaphysics of the particle population, this chapter outlines how a tabular and spiral form of The Periodic Table of the Elements provides on the one hand, a clear picture of the physical and chemical nature of these elements. And on the other, how all the elements are located on a single path that in effect brings the particles like pilgrims from the fringe element of Uranium to the universal elementary state we know as Hydrogen.

Reader, I hope and trust that you are familiar with "The Periodic Table of the Elements". The table maps the existence of a periodic law, that governs the order amongst the 94 elements of matter. The Table was initially developed by the Russian chemist Dmitri Mendeleev, in 1869. He arranged the elements in order of their atomic numbers and a recurrence of their physical

properties then becomes evident. Elements in the same group tend to show similar chemical characteristics.

The periodic table is now a central and indispensable part of modern chemistry and provided a foundation for the Western World to develop its' impressive knowledge of the material world, and how to create complex chemicals that serve society.

Here, in a quest to see and value the metaphysical nature of our Universe, I would advocate an equal interest in this spiral pattern which in fact presents the same information as is in the rectangular table, but now with an emphasis on an evolving story that builds on the evidence coming mainly from our nuclear work, of how the particle population is

social and sentient, more than we have so far cared or dared to consider.

I will outline the story, the reality, that the whole spiral pattern presents as an overview of the lively and evolving nature of the particle population.

Firstly, the main dynamic of the spiral is the way it shows how all the ninety four elements line up and co-exist on a single path that looks to have a purposeful destination. A path that begins nominally with the element Uranium, located at the very edge of what looks like a mountain or it could be a whirlpool. The idea looks obvious and makes good sense, that the particle population as an whole are migrating along this one path. A path, a pilgrim journey, that brings itinerant nomadic/migrant particles from their first ever social settlement (the relatively large gregarious atoms of elemental uranium), to then step out on an evolving journey that moves them individually and collectively through the sequence of elements wherein they are, as it were, schooled and socialised and strengthened until in time they are transformed, centred and self-disciplined, enough that they become as atoms of hydrogen, which is in effect the simplest and most stable and abundant element in the whole Universe.

I am moved to like this analogy for the way it recognises and values the social and sentient and spiritual nature of the particle population. Sees how they are responsible in themselves for this journey to discover their universal nature. When we register the evidence of "energetic symmetry" at work in every dimension of this universal system we are within, then it also makes sense to see that we humans are equally caught up over time in an evolving pilgrimage, seeking to become as the metaphysical equivalent of elemental hydrogen.

This overview of the particle world brought me to look again into the processes of nuclear fission. In this mood, I will develop an account of the process we know as the "enrichment of uranium". I think it important and courteous and wise above all else that we see and treat this next level of life in this shared universal system, with the same respect and curiosity we have for our neighbours. The atomic particles being in fact our nearest neighbours in the whole Universe.

Dualistic perceptions of the particle world.

The particles are as small to us humans as we are small to the Sun. This insight (it's not exactly correct) helps us picture the physical symmetry that is built into the universal system we are within. The insight that complements this is how it is the same energy, the same four forces, that are at work within and between the populations who reside in each dimension. This information in turn indicates how the particles are as pre-occupied with relationships and family life and raising their electron children as we humans are. Meanwhile our nuclear work works for us by splitting up the large loosely-bound egalitarian atoms of uranium, which then releases a torrent of painfully sad and despairing feelings. Here, for me, is a sure sign that the particles are supremely sentient as well as being highly social.

The Periodic Table of the Elements

Legend:
 — Atomic Number
 — Element Symbol
 — Element Name
 — Average Atomic Mass

1	2											10	11	12			
H Hydrogen 1.008	He Helium 4.003											Ne Neon 20.18	Ar Argon 39.95	Kr Krypton 83.80			
3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18		
Li Lithium 6.94	Be Beryllium 9.01	B Boron 10.81	C Carbon 12.01	N Nitrogen 14.01	O Oxygen 16.00	F Fluorine 18.99	Ne Neon 20.18	Na Sodium 22.99	Mg Magnesium 24.31	Al Aluminum 26.98	Si Silicon 28.09	P Phosphorus 30.97	S Sulfur 32.07	Cl Chlorine 35.45	Ar Argon 39.95		
19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
K Potassium 39.10	Ca Calcium 40.08	Sc Scandium 44.96	Ti Titanium 47.88	V Vanadium 50.94	Cr Chromium 52.00	Mn Manganese 54.94	Fe Iron 55.85	Co Cobalt 58.93	Ni Nickel 58.69	Cu Copper 63.55	Zn Zinc 65.39	Ga Gallium 69.72	Ge Germanium 72.64	As Arsenic 74.92	Se Selenium 78.96	Br Bromine 79.90	Kr Krypton 83.80
37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54
Rb Rubidium 85.47	Sr Strontium 87.62	Y Yttrium 88.91	Zr Zirconium 91.22	Nb Niobium 92.91	Mo Molybdenum 95.94	Tc Technetium 98.91	Ru Ruthenium 101.07	Rh Rhodium 102.91	Pd Palladium 106.42	Ag Silver 107.87	Cd Cadmium 112.41	In Indium 114.82	Sn Tin 118.71	Sb Antimony 121.76	Te Tellurium 127.60	I Iodine 126.91	Xe Xenon 131.29
55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72
Cs Cesium 132.91	Ba Barium 137.33	La Lanthanum 138.91	Hf Hafnium 178.49	Ta Tantalum 180.95	W Tungsten 183.84	Re Rhenium 186.21	Os Osmium 190.23	Ir Iridium 192.22	Pt Platinum 195.08	Au Gold 196.97	Hg Mercury 200.59	Tl Thallium 204.38	Pb Lead 207.2	Bi Bismuth 208.98	Po Polonium 209	At Astatine 210	Rn Radon 222
87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100	101	102	103	104
Fr Francium 223	Ra Radium 226	Ac Actinium 227	Rf Rutherfordium 261	Db Dubnium 262	Sg Seaborgium 266	Bh Bohrium 264	Hs Hassium 269	Mt Meitnerium 268	Ds Darmstadtium 271	Rg Roentgenium 272	Cn Copernicium 285	Fl Flerovium 287	Lv Livermorium 293	Ts Tennessine 289	Og Oganesson 294	Lr Lawrencium 260	
73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90
Lu Lutetium 174.97	Hf Hafnium 178.49	Ta Tantalum 180.95	W Tungsten 183.84	Re Rhenium 186.21	Os Osmium 190.23	Ir Iridium 192.22	Pt Platinum 195.08	Au Gold 196.97	Hg Mercury 200.59	Tl Thallium 204.38	Pb Lead 207.2	Bi Bismuth 208.98	Po Polonium 209	At Astatine 210	Rn Radon 222	Lr Lawrencium 260	

This account seeks to develop a dualistic knowledge of the process we know as “the enrichment of Uranium”. The dualistic view is achieved by outlining, in the first instance, the physics of the atoms that together form elemental Uranium. This account is accompanied by a commentary on the metaphysics of the particle population who together form the tribal groups that combine to form the particle nation of Uranium. It's all a bit long winded, but my concern for this process brought me to unpack it, that we can see the cold-hearted aloofness of our nuclear work.

I need to say once again how I believe we humans, we Humanity, need to develop a dualistic view of the Atomic realm, one that is equally invested in the physics and the metaphysics of this "next floor down" world.

The enrichment of Uranium. This account seeks to develop a dualistic knowledge of the process we know as “the enrichment of Uranium”. The dualistic view is achieved by outlining, in the first instance, the physics of the atoms that together form elemental Uranium. This knowledge is accompanied in turn by a commentary on the metaphysics of the particle population, their behaviour, their apparent concern for others. My thesis is about our need to look both ways, treat objective and subjective information as being of equal value..

Seeking to pin down this amalgam of two very different but complementary views of the Atomic realm, I'd suggest they combine the White-man's disciplined inquiring objective mind with Black-woman's earthy awareness of the universality of family processes which extend seamlessly throughout the world of the atomic particles.

A concern for the inner working of the enrichment process requires in the first place a general understanding of the atomic nature of elemental uranium. This is the kind of information that nuclear physics excels at determining, that lets us how we know that elemental uranium is primarily formed of two 'isotopes', which are analogous to there being two tribal groups that together form the whole particle nation of Uranium. There are many other isotopes which are part of the Uranium nation, but they are generally so small or short-lived, they will not feature in this discussion.

The two tribes have been pragmatically named by physics as **U-235 and U-238**. (The number refers to a system of classification which records the number of protons and electrons in the atoms of each element).

U-238 is by far the largest, most numerous, isotope/tribe. It comprises 99.28% of the whole Uranium nation. It is in fact so dominant that the generally stable, dense, settled nature of this isotope creates a metallic element with these same qualities.

The secondary tribal, whom we know as **U-235**, forms 0.71 % of the whole uranium nation. This is equivalent to one atom, one family system of the **U-235 tribe**, living amongst one hundred and forty atoms or family units of the abundant and dominant **U-238 tribe**.

In metaphysical terms, we need to note that while the big **U-238** tribe is a settled, complacent, civil society (we might even say – bourgeois), the very minor **U-235** tribal atoms are by nature solitary and anti-social and scattered throughout the bulk of the body of the Uranium nation. However, at an early stage of our human exploration of the Atomic Continent, the **U-235** tribe was recognised as being somewhat unstable. Physics labels it as 'fissile'. It is edgy and nervous, needs its' space, especially from the other **U-235** family units.

In this context, it looks as though the big **U-238** tribe has taken it upon itself to host and even mentor this small percentage of disaffected atoms, who have always been part of the whole uranium nation. They will have made the journey together, from wherever it was that they came from. Possibly an exploding star system. To arrive and contribute to the creation of this planet with only 0.71% of the immigrants unable to participate in working the new land is, statistically speaking, a very acceptable and commendable rate of health for any one society. It seems possible to me that the big **U-238** tribe host and support the irritable and tetchy **U-235** households because they too where like them at one time, needing solitude and acceptance and friendship to deal with and emerge from the hardships of their journey.

The early explorers of the Atomic continent soon came to recognise the prickly hostile nature of this very small-in-numbers tribe of atoms. But it woke the idea that the **U-235 atoms** could be retrieved from their isolated existence and then put together with their own kind to form a much larger group. Here their nervous energy would simmer and ferment with the others and make for an unusually group of fissile atoms now fizzing with tension and anger and suicidal thoughts. It would not take much then, to bring them to a point where they triggered each other and thereby initiated a much larger fission process that sucked in the plebeian **U-238** atoms.

The engineers determined the critical ratio at which point the fission process would begin. This set another group of engineers the task of 'enriching' the normal Uranium nation with an infusion of the troublesome **U-235** tribe. The first atomic bombs were made with up to 90% **U-235**. This stuff fissions in an instant, releasing in a single moment all of the Light that is normally in each atom, in each family unit. Then there is a shockwave atom, which I imagine is formed by the three kinds of Love that are or were in each atom. And then there is a great outpouring of the stuff we know as radiation, which to my mind is a measure of the despair and sadness of the vast throng of atomic particles who see and feel their homes, their families, their nation shredded in a moment of our time.

Uranium destined for the nuclear reactors is enriched to about 4 % U-235. This helps the normally passive U-238 to burn steadily, perhaps with indignation, alongside of the families they had been hosting.

The devastation of the families who form the uranium nation is hard to accept. What goes on inside our nuclear reactors is virtually identical to the African Slave Trade. The distress of the particles requires major expenditure to pay for shielding the fission process and residue, that no one at any stage will feel or hear any part the process.

Civil society would be wise to create a disciplined and managed way for a group of women and men to experience the emotional content of radiation. That we become knowledgeable instead of fearful of the processes involved. Then we can explore ideas of how civil society might participate and develop 'energetic process' that respond to the un-natural technologies we have inherited from previous generations.

There is much to be gained by looking into the Atomic World as anthropologists, as concerned-citizens, as curious civilians, as Samaritans (should you be Christian), or simply as neighbours. Lest we forget, the atomic particles are the children of this universal system we are within. The real adventure of all our nuclear work will come when we acquire the social skills to love and care for the ethnically cleansed **U-235 tribe**, and help them settle. Then we will be moving in a remarkably positive and adventurous direction.

I was, I am, blessed to have had a childhood in Kenya. Influenced by Maria, I could not help but absorb a quotient of the earthy consciousness of Africa, of African people. I have this memory of walking beside her one time and kicking a stone at the side of the road. She stopped and remonstrated with me. Many creatures live underneath that stone, she instructed me. She bent down and turned it over slowly. Centipedes and a scorpion and ants and other little creatures were startled by this intrusion and scurried away. Her attitude of care went towards everything. I see it still in this photograph. The tranquility that emanated from her. I like to think her example helped me years later to listen and acknowledge the pain and distress in the hot atmosphere of that laboratory built into the back-end of the reactor.

That was good engineering practice, to monitor the vulnerable places. But then, the way we limit our curiosity and shield ourselves from the body of information that is even able to seep through concrete walls. It makes no sense at all. An apartheid attitude has crept into our outlook and treatment of the atomic particles. History is repeating itself in so many ways. We white people are repeating ourselves in too many ways.

5. The energetic symmetry that infuses our Universe indicates the potential we humans have to create a remedial process whereby we might land photons of our Love and Light amongst the fissioned particles, to determine if this is beneficial for them.

In contrast to the White-man's technology which works to 'split the atom', African society looks capable of developing a collective spiritual process able to 'heal the atom'.

I prepared this 'five part paper' to highlight the "energetic symmetry" that is evident at every level of our Universe. This profound understanding comes from viewing the heavens above and the atoms below with what I think of as an "African consciousness". This approach sees the experiential nature of phenomena which then complements the objective knowledge that the Western mind excels at collecting. My sense is that by combining the knowledge that comes from looking both way, we begin to see the universal nature of our Universe.

This whole understanding found a home in me as a consequence of my childhood in Kenya where I was influenced on the one hand by my British parents, and on the other by simply living simply amongst African people in a landscape barely touched by modernity. I am far from being the first to observe this principle of universal symmetry. The civilisations of Ancient Egypt saw it for themselves, and described the whole effect with the simple phrase ... "As above, so below".

In our time, this same concept of universal symmetry is becoming known as the "holographic nature of our Universe".

The Christian view of this principle finds expression in the statement Christ made to his followers when he said: "In my Father's house are many rooms,"

In my understanding, He was implying that we humans live in just this one room, this one dimension of our Universe. But the time will come when we will realise there are many dimensions, many rooms, to the whole universal system that we are within. We are familiar already with the 'room' above us, being as the home of the Moon and the Sun, while the room below and inside of where and who we are, is the Atomic realm, home for the particle population.

Black and white observations tell us that the same 'four kinds of energy' are in each room. Three of these are forms of Love, while the fourth is a form of Light.

This children's ditty casually describes the very same principle:

**Big fleas have little fleas, upon their backs to bite 'em.
And little fleas have lesser fleas, and so ... ad infinitum.**

The series of internally-stacking Russian Dolls provides an excellent example of an 'holographic system'. As do our own personal families, with each generation nestled inside of the preceding one.

The knowledge needs to go round, of the atomic particles being social and sentient, the same as us humans. The sentience of the atomic particles can really only be known by getting out of our safety mentality and experiencing the feeling of what nuclear radiation feels like. Then we'll get some idea of the suffering of the fissioned particles. Radioactivity is measure of their despair and sadness.

I can write like this only because I worked at a nuclear reactor and found a place where I could experience the extraordinary distress emanating from spent fuel rods. This discharge of negative emotions suggests to me that the fissioned particles will be hugely receptive to the experience of being loved, of being at the receiving end of a collective expression of Love and warm thoughts from a group of women and men, seeking to combine these forces that live within us.

galactic magnitude

sun, moon, earth system

human family

particle families

This is family work. But now at a scale we have not explored so far. Nonetheless, Humanity has an instinct for working together to nurture our children's world, along with the animals and plants whom we have domesticated, who move in with us because they like the experience of being cared for and loved, even if it is imperfectly done. No one else gives it to them.

In this mood, I think the stage is set for us humans to experiment and develop group processes whereby we might seek to create quantum units of the two fundamental forces, 'feminine power' and 'masculine strength', that one way or another have a home in all of us. The same qualities as are in the light of the Moon and the light of the Sun. The same as they are in the neutrons and protons who together form the nucleus of 'atoms'. In metaphysical terms, we'll be learning to make 'photons', to convey what are in effect units of our universal energy, to land in the next level down from where we are. In this context, the atomic particles are as the children of our Universe. This understanding signifies how we humans, we Humanity, need to work collectively to be as effective parents or god-parents for the particle world.

I sense we are on watch, on duty for the well-being of the whole Atomic realm, the same as the Moon and the Sun are on watch and committed to care for the Earth and us earthlings, and everything that lives here. We are part of a long series of family systems which we can not really know how or where it all began, and how it might go on. Was the Big Bang formative. Our Western mind gravitates to this idea. Are the atomic particles responsible for the well-being of the dimension downstairs and inside of where they are? It feels very possible. If we align with this whole picture, I feel we will be going in the right direction. Right for us, with room for future generations to see if it works for them.

I am moved by experience to believe that singing together is the engine room for this venture to 'heal the atom'. I'll leave the idea there, without much more direction than recounting how I have attended and participated in collective celebrations and devotions and religious practice(s) in East and South Africa. The experiences incline me to say how African people have an instinct for collective work which I see as essential for developing an healing process for the dis-ease we know as radioactivity. If we can reach down into the Atomic realm with our home-made photons, and top up or wash down the radioactive particles with units of our Love and Light, then I think we will be opening a door to the future.

I think already that the nuclear nations will be glad to know that this kind of work is being considered. If it is successful, then we have a social technology able to address the issues of the radioactive waste materials accumulating alongside each reactor. The funds being set aside to pay for the underground repositories that each nation plans to develop would surely be due any group or national body who has an aptitude for an healing approach to the radioactive materials.

Dear Women, the whole nuclear subject especially needs your interest and involvement. The Atomic World, viewed with a feminine gaze, feels to be more social and sentient than we have so far cared or dared to consider. Matriarchal experience and acumen helps us realise the whole social nature of this next-floor-down realm with its vast population of family systems. They are as busy as we are with relationships, with the demands of family life, with raising their electron children while interacting positively with their neighbours and neighbourhood.

Becoming a parent myself, being in a steady relationship with a steadfast woman, raising children together, registering the pre-conceptual views of the children themselves, all of this helped me enormously to realise the family processes going on in the Atomic World.

Now we clever men have developed the fission process, which works for us by breaking up the large community-like atoms that form the element Uranium. Fission causes the four kinds of energy that are at work and play between the particles in each atom, to come free and be available for our use.

Your moonlight and tenderness, your electromagnetic field, is balm for wounded and hurting people. It will surely be the same for the radioactive particles. Only that the atomic particles are in effect as small to us humans as we are small to the Sun, that we need to work out how to amplify and focus y/our power (says the man in me), that 'she' can be felt down in the landscape where they are. Yet I sense that the substantial change of magnitude between the dimension that we humans live within and the atomic dimension means that we will have quite some leverage in our favour, if and when we engage with them. We men can hold the door, warm the room, whatever is required to help your tribe gather and work together. Healing the atom, addressing the dis-ease and distress of the particle population, looks to be an attribute of your whole nature.

I have the idea that a common household smoke detector, devices that are powered by a tiny chip of Americium 141 (a radioactive isotope created in a nuclear reactor) can serve as a monitor for this civilian adventure, that can quickly learn if the 'photons' that we might create and direct to land amongst the radioactive particles, are affective in alleviating their distress.

A radioactive chip is used in this device because the negative ions that the chip emits are used to create a small electric current that tests - as it jumps an air-gap - if smoke particles are in the air. If they are, the flow of ions is blocked, and the electric current ceases. At which point the devise is programmed to sounds its alarm.

My thinking is that if the group's singing can land a photon pulsating with Love and Light amongst the radioactive particles, might this cause the radioactive particles to cease discharging their negative emotions, if only for a nanosecond. That would be enough to stop the electric current, at which point the alarm would sound. In effect signalling - thank you for your love and concern. We feel it and relax, feel better and cease emitting our signal of distress.

I can imagine there are more sophisticated or perhaps simpler ways to determine if we can ameliorate the distress of radioactive particles. May they all succeed, and us too, in exploring how we might communicate with the particle world.

Closing thoughts.

The insight that came from my childhood in northern Kenya, of seeing on many occasions how the Moon and the Sun are the same apparent size, this helped me to see how there is an inside and outside way of viewing our planetary system, and both are good. This realisation prepared me to look down into the particle world and see how the atomic particles are social and sentient, the same as ourselves.

Observing the wholeness and holiness of the heavenly Light that we are within, prepares us to see the Atomic World in the same way. We can not forego or forget our nuclear knowledge. There is no going back. The only way out then is to go in deeper. Look with more care. Care more about how we look. Observe the family nature of this dynamic multi-tiered universal system we are within and recognise our ability to work together and develop a positive and loving relationship and approach to the particle population. Metaphorically, they are as the children of our Universe.

If a collective spiritual approach to the particle realm proves able to ameliorate the phenomena of radiation, then we will have a social technology in our back pocket that can be brought in the first instance to address the fairly substantial radioactive waste issues that our abundant use of nuclear reactors has created. This same healing process could in turn be used to stabilise the unstable elements, typically enriched uranium and plutonium, which would then make nuclear weapons vulnerable and mutable, more than has so far been anticipated.

As with begetting children, our awareness and concern for the Atomic World will be with us and part of our human story, now and forever more. This means we have long term duties of care and responsibility for the particle world that will need to be part of daily life. Our responsibilities are expanding. How else can it be when we live in an expanding and symmetrical Universe. The future looks remarkably adventurous, with our quest to explore the outer Universe matched by the need to look inwards and know our own universal nature. The one nourishing the other. Now, good wishes for the shared dreaming and work that can take us into the future.

Asante, nimefurahi kukutana nawe.
Mambo yote yaende sawa kwako na kwa watu wako.

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